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STATE REGULATION OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY: EXPERIENCE OF THE COUNTRIES OF THE WORLD

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Abstract. The authors compare the specifics of state regulation of circular economy: experience of the countries of the world. The authors show that at the end of the last century, the efforts of legislators in the field of limiting the uncontrolled growth of the use of packaging materials, requirements for recycling and its multiple use in order to protect the environment became a priority. The authors note that the improvement of the waste management system was recognized as the main problem in the field of environmental protection at the end of the first – the beginning of the second millennium, therefore the first measures in the EU were aimed at the safe placement of waste at existing landfills. The authors conclude that economically developed countries in Europe, North America and Asia with developed waste recycling programs have come to the conclusion that the most difficult tasks during waste processing are the following: (1) creation of an effective system of separate collection of solid waste; (2) increase in the commercial value of secondary raw materials.

Keywords: circular economy, state regulation, waste recycling programs, waste processing.

Introduction. In the current conditions in the developing countries, the activity of the government and non-governmental organizations, as well as business representatives in the formation of a circular economy is insufficient, which is confirmed by the low values of reuse and disposal of products and waste and the low requirements of environmental legislation for the formation of closed-loop productions. The above determines the relevance and necessity of formation and development of the circular economy in developing countries in accordance with the experience of the EU countries.

Literature review. The article (Erick Hungaro Arruda, Rosângela Andrade Pita Brancalhão Melatto, Wilson Levy & Diego de Melo Conti, 2021) is aimed at presenting different perspectives and concepts of circular economy. Accordingly, a qualitative study was carried out and the methodology of a systematic review of the literature was applied in order to obtain thorough knowledge about the topic using the latest and current articles. As a result, an extract of researched articles and a comparison of scientific literature on this topic is presented, demonstrating some evolution of aspects of circular economy, such as the design of new products, the formation of new legislation and the introduction of the principles of circular economy by industry. Although the study was not convincing as to how the evolution of circular economy would occur, the authors propose future studies to assess the transition to circular economy. It is also recommended that future studies consider case studies as a model for assessing the progress of circular economy concerning legislation and economic interests.

The authors of the work (Oliveira, M., Miguel, M., van Langen, S.K. et al., 2021) believe that the concept of circular economy has recently gained popularity in political debates and corporate discourse around the world as a path to sustainable development. Academic debate is characterized by several sometimes very

contrasting definitions of the concept. Here, the authors argue that a clearer definition is needed for the concept of circular economy in terms of strategies, goals, future states, and stakeholder needs. The authors also emphasize that it is necessary to develop assessment methods to track the transition to a circular economy. In this context, this article establishes the need for a multilateral, multidimensional and multi-criteria approach to assess the transition to circular economy on different time and spatial scales, as well as several sustainability dimensions.

The study (Lamba, H.K., Kumar, N.S. & Dhir, S., 2024) theoretically explores existing literature published on circular economy and sustainable development to identify significant research topics of the most relevant authors, countries and journals. Systematically reviewing 596 scientific articles, significant research topics in this area were found. They include frameworks and indicators for defining and evaluating circular economy, circular business models and their use cases, global and industrial contexts for the application of circular economy, and various dimensions of circular economy. Publications from only one database were used. Only articles published in relevant academic journals were used for bibliometric analysis. Only articles with a large number of citations were selected for joint citation analysis and cluster formation.

The authors of the paper (Anupam Khajuria, Vella A. Atienza, Suchana Chavanich, Wilts Henning, Ishrat Islam, Ulrich Kral, Meng Liu, Xiao Liu, Indu K. Murthy, Temitope D. Timothy Oyedotun, Prabhat Verma, Guochang Xu, Xianlai Zeng & Jinhui Li, 2022) note that circular economy seems to be a vital means for sustainable use of natural resources, which is also important to achieve the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. Therefore, special issues of "sustainable solutions and effective practices in the circular economy" were considered at the 16th International Conference on Waste Management and Technology, where researchers and participants shared their experiences and opinions. Presentations were presented

with a focus on many key points, such as new strategies, innovative technologies, management and methods of circular economy. These presentations gave an idea of promising ways of developing a circular economy. The authors summarize that the transition to a circular economy can preserve the value of resources and products at a high level, as well as ensuring the minimization of waste production.

Accordingly, the purpose of the work is to compare the specifics of state regulation of circular economy: experience of the countries of the world.

Methodology

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study are the fundamental provisions of the theory of state regulation of circular economy. To solve the problems of work, the following methods of general and special scientific knowledge were used:

- hypothetical-deductive - to clarify the essence of the subject of study;
- system-analytical - to assess the structure and specifics of the functioning of the mechanisms of state regulation of the formation and development of the circular economy;
- categorical analysis - to substantiate the theoretical foundations of the formation of the state target complex policy in the field of circular economy development;
- analysis and comparison of trends - to track the dynamics of changes in the volume of recycling and processing of solid household waste in different countries.

Main part

Despite the difference in the methods of state regulation of waste in many countries, the common thing is that the state sets the goals of environmental policy of waste management, determines its priorities and develops norms of relations with nature users, that is, the economic mechanism. This mechanism itself functions on a

market basis with elements of coercive measures of both economic and non-economic nature .

At the end of the last century, the efforts of legislators in the field of limiting the uncontrolled growth of the use of packaging materials, requirements for recycling and its multiple use in order to protect the environment became a priority.

In order to optimize the processes of collection and processing of packaging waste, on December 20, 1994, the European Parliament together with the European Council adopted the European Directive on packaging and packaging waste (No. 94/62/EC). This directive provides uniform mandatory packaging requirements for all EU member states. Without their compliance, the product cannot be admitted to the European single market [; 6].

In order to implement the Directive in many European countries, relevant national legislative acts and resolutions were adopted, on the basis of which the state strategy for the separate collection and recycling of packaging waste is being built. In accordance with this Directive, an additional environmental tax is introduced on all types of packaging, which is used exclusively for its intended purpose – for the development of recycling of packaging materials [1; 5].

The analysis of the circular economy, projects for the implementation of its individual elements and a strategy for its development as a whole are urgent issues for developing countries in connection with significant environmental problems, among which the following can be distinguished:

– according to official accounting data, about 35 billion tons of waste are accumulated only in Ukraine, the volume of which increases by 5 billion tons annually; in addition to this, 8–9 million tons are accounted for by non-centralized removal of municipal solid waste (hereinafter – MSW) with burial in uncontrolled landfills; the volume of hazardous waste per capita is 4 times higher than the level characteristic of EU countries;

– more than 90% of all solid waste generated is sent to burial; removal to waste processing plants is slightly more than 8% of their total volume; organized landfills and unauthorized landfills occupy a total area of 47.7 thousand hectares;

– the unacceptably high level of material intensity of the economy and its raw material specialization serve as a key factor in the significant burden on the environment; extraction, production, processing and transportation of natural raw materials account for 87% of greenhouse gas emissions, 76% of harmful emissions into the atmosphere, 77% of polluted water discharges and 97% of industrial waste from their total volume;

– economic losses and damages caused by environmental pollution and deterioration of the quality of natural resources in the country reach 4–6% of GDP, and taking into account the negative consequences for human health, 10–15% of GDP [3; 8].

Global environmental problems, which are manifested in developing countries and require immediate solutions, can be overcome with the help of the development of a circular economy.

Let's consider the best experience of creating conditions for the development of a circular economy.

The European Remanufacturing Network (ERN) Project was launched in the EU in 2015, aimed at bringing together the government, manufacturers and the scientific community to develop remanufacturing in the region through market research, collection and analysis of best practices and business models. Also, the EU has adopted a number of initiatives by the state and private individuals, among which the following stand out:

- the circular economy package published in 2014, which includes the general communication COM(2014)398, which proposes changes to aspects of six EU waste directives COM(2014)397, and also provides measures for the sustainability of

buildings (COM(2014)445), environmental employment (COM(2014)446) and other environmental actions (COM(2014)440);

- implementation of the roadmap for resource conservation in the EU (COM(2011)571), the Seventh EU Environmental Action Program – 7th EAP (Decision No 1386/2013/EU) and recommendations for the European Resource Efficiency Platform (EREP);

- work for the period after 2015 of the development program and development of global goals in the field of sustainable development;

- implementation of the "Europe 2020" strategy, among other relevant road maps and flagship initiatives to improve the efficiency of resource use (Innovation Union, Industrial Policy, Skills and Jobs);

- participation in the G7 Alliance for resource efficiency [9; 12].

The interaction between the above-mentioned initiatives reduces the barriers to the transformation of the linear economy into a circular form.

Thus, one of the priority areas of activity within the G7 is the development of remanufacturing and ecological design of products, which are key components of the circular economy. One of the main goals of the Seventh Environmental Action Program of the EU is to increase the efficiency of resource use and the formation of a "green" economy, which also fully meets the objectives of the formation of a circular economy. In addition, the Circular Economy Package, adopted in 2014, is the harmonization of various regulatory and legislative acts, as well as the reduction of contradictions between the adopted programs and initiatives. This Package includes an Action Plan that covers the entire production and economic cycle, starting with the production and consumption of products and ending with waste disposal and the market for secondary raw materials and changing the regulatory and legal regulation of waste management with high target indicators. Among these indicators, it is possible to highlight the disposal of 65% of household waste and 75% of packaging

materials by 2030, the reduction of landfill areas by 10%, etc. All this shows that the Action Plan is aimed at involving a wide range of stakeholders in various sectors, not only EU member states, but also other states [4; 8; 12].

In the formation of the circular economy and the development of its principles in practice, participants of a number of non-governmental initiatives and organizations play an active role, which include the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, the Dutch Circle organization, the European Union's Horizon 2020 research program, and others.

The government of Singapore also finances the development of remanufacturing. Thus, in 2012, the ARTC Center was organized there to develop better technologies and recovery opportunities. Several leading multinational corporations such as Rolls-Royce, Siemens Industry, ABB, TruMarine and JPT Electronics have signed a memorandum of cooperation with ARTC to work together on remanufacturing technology challenges in the aerospace, oil and gas, marine, energy and automotive industries. The Malaysian government has also funded market research to develop remanufacturing and industry in its country. The Chinese government is developing the concept of circular economy as a vital strategy to achieve the goals of sustainable development [3; 7; 11].

All this points led to the growing attention to the development of the circular economy by governments and non-governmental organizations in many countries, which is due to high positive environmental, social and economic effects.

In fact, the existing scheme for handling waste and end-of-life products is aimed at supporting and developing the circular economy, because it contains the main elements of the latter, with the help of which a closed life cycle of the product is formed, with the exception of disposal in landfills. It is worth noting that legislation in the EU was formed for many years, the first Framework Directive on waste 75/442/EEC was adopted on July 15, 1975, and the general provisions of the

European Union on ecology and resource consumption (which also include waste management) are set out in the founding EU treaty back in 1957. At the same time, all standards become mandatory only after a few years to ensure the possibility of economic and technical training of enterprises [2; 5; 9].

The improvement of the waste management system was recognized as the main problem in the field of environmental protection at the end of the first – the beginning of the second millennium, therefore the first measures in the EU were aimed at the safe placement of waste at existing landfills, in particular, Directive 99/31/EC "About burying waste at landfills" was adopted in 1999. But already in 2008, in the Directive 2008/98/EC "On waste" the main principle became the prevention of waste generation.

The next goal was to create conditions and incentives for reuse and recovery of products. A number of legislative and regulatory acts are aimed at this, including Directive 2000/53/EC on end-of-life vehicles and Directive 2012/19/EC on electronic equipment.

In modern conditions, the solution of the given problem contributes to the adoption of the new version of the international environmental management standard ISO 14001:2015, which emphasizes the concept of the product life cycle, taking into account the possibility of its use or restoration at the end of operation. Due to the fact that not all types of products are subject to recovery and reuse, products unsuitable for these purposes should be processed to obtain raw materials. In addition, Directive 94/62/EC was passed in 1994, which mandated the recycling of 50% of metal, 60% of glass, paper/cardboard and 22.5% of plastic by 2008. As a result, today some types of products, for example, car batteries, must be recycled by 100% [3; 4; 10].

At the same time, it should be noted that the structure of waste management in EU countries in recent years looks like this (Table 1).

Table 1

The structure of waste management in EU countries in recent years

A type of waste management	Percentage of the total amount of waste
Processing	30%
Composting	17%
Combustion	28%
Burial in landfills	24%

Source: compiled on the basis of [3; 8]

Besides, it should be noted that the situation regarding waste management has significantly improved in recent years in the EU countries (Table 2).

Table 2

The structure of waste management in EU countries in the previous decade

A type of waste management	Percentage of the total amount of waste
Processing	24%
Composting	13 %
Combustion	21%
Burial in landfills	43%

Source: compiled on the basis of [; 8]

In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that of the 25 countries mentioned in the Eurostat report, the largest amount of garbage is produced by the following countries (Table 3).

Table 3

EU countries producing the largest amount of waste

Country	Volumes of waste, kg/person
Denmark	781
Cyprus	637
Germany	633
Luxembourg	607
Malta	604

Source: compiled on the basis of [9; 12]

From the table 3 it can be seen that Denmark produces the largest amount of garbage among EU countries (781 kg of garbage per person).

At the same time, it should be noted that the following amounts of fines for non-compliance with environmental legislation are present in the EU countries (Table 4).

Table 4

Fines for non-compliance with environmental legislation in EU countries

Type of violation	The amount of the fine, €
Minor violation by households	450
Clogging of forests with waste from individuals	850

Source: compiled on the basis of [9; 12]

Currently, EU countries have established norms regarding mandatory separate collection of household waste (Table 5).

Table 5

Fines for non-compliance with environmental legislation in EU countries

Type of household waste	Percentage of the total amount of waste, %
Plastic, glass, metal, paper	30
Bio waste	37

Source: compiled on the basis of [3; 8; 9]

It should be noted that in 2015, the EU adopted a package of measures on waste recycling within the framework of the circular economy with the aim of bringing the level of waste recycling up to 65% by 2035.

Conclusions

Thus, economically developed countries in Europe, North America and Asia with developed waste recycling programs have come to the conclusion that the most difficult tasks during waste processing are the following:

- creation of an effective system of separate collection of solid waste;
- increase in the commercial value of secondary raw materials.

Separate collection of waste with subsequent return of the collected fractions of waste to economic circulation in most developed countries is gradually becoming one of the most promising methods of solving the solid waste problem.

Discussion

According to the EU waste management scheme, a part of the products and waste that is not suitable for processing should be used to obtain energy and fertilizers through incineration or for composting. Therefore, in 2000, Directive 2000/76/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of Europe "On waste incineration" was adopted, which established maximum permissible emission standards for waste incineration plants. Only in the case of exhausting the possibilities associated with the application of all the listed methods, waste in the EU

should be cleaned and neutralized, and then buried in a landfill, which, however, does not belong to the processes of the circular economy and is subject to cancellation in the event of the spread of its principles.

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